

Novel Imidazole Congeners as Anti-inflammatory Agents

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Amino acids are the precursors of various macromolecules in the biological system and they play a prominent role in the pathophysiology of inflammation^{1,2}. Our earlier studies have shown that aminoacyl benzoate derivatives. Furthermore imidazoles³ possess anti-inflammatory activity. In the present study, we have synthesised novel congeners by incorporating these two moieties to obtain potent anti-inflammatory agents

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) *o*-Phenylenediamine, (ii) N-protected amino acid, CH_2Cl_2 , dicyclohexylcarbodiimide and (iii) NaOH , C_6H_6 .

N-Arylmethylene-2-methyl-5-4*H*-oxazoline (1) was fused with *o*-phenylenediamine to yield β -amino-*N*-2-(4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene)-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl (2). The primary amino group in compound 2 was coupled with different N-protected amino acids in presence of dicyclohexylcarbodiimide and methylene chloride to yield β -amino-*N*-(2-(4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene)-1*H*-imidazole-1-yl)phenylaminoacyl benzoate (3). It was subjected to debenzoylation in basic medium using dry benzene to give β -amino-*N*-2-(4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene)-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl)phenyl-substituted-amides (4) which is provided with *o*-phenyl amino amidic side-chain (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3 AND 4*

Compd. no.	Ar	R	M.p. °C
3a	C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	102
b	C_6H_5	H	156
c	C_6H_5	CH_3	177
d	C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	88
e	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	142
f	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	H	196
g	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	CH_3	116
h	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	122
i	2-OH. C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	102
j	2-OH. C_6H_5	H	144
k	2-OH. C_6H_5	CH_3	164
l	2-OH. C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	158
m	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	176
n	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	H	166
o	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	CH_3	210
p	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	151
4a	C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	172
b	C_6H_5	H	116
c	C_6H_5	CH_3	110
d	C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	152
e	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	90
f	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	H	140
g	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	CH_3	152
h	4- N -(CH_3) ₂ C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	164
i	4-OH. C_6H_5	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	164
j	4-OH. C_6H_5	H	192
k	4-OH. C_6H_5	CH_3	96
l	4-OH. C_6H_5	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	112
m	3,5-(CCH_3) ₂ C_6H_4	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$	98
n	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_4	H	110
o	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_4	CH_3	176
p	3,5-(OCH_3) ₂ C_6H_4	$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$	194

* All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

Antiinflammatory activity was determined by the reported method⁴. The degree of protection provided by compounds 4a—p at 100 mg/kg p.o. against carrageenin induced rat's paw oedema ranged from 2.9 to 57.8%. Protection with some

of these compounds viz. 4a, b and d was comparable to that of the reference standard drug phenylbutazone (51.46%) in the identical doses. Structure-activity relationship (SAR) studies showed that among four group of compounds, 4a, b and d showed potent antiinflammatory activity. 4a which has phenylmethylene at position-4 and aminophenylbenzenepropanamide at position-1 of imidazole nucleus exhibited maximum activity (57.8%) whereas 4b and d having aminophenylacetamide and aminophenyl-3-*p*-methylbutanamide present at position-1 of the imidazole moiety showed 50.1 and 50.7% activity respectively. Compounds 4e and l in which imidazoline ring was substituted with aminophenylbenzenepropanamide and aminophenyl-3-methylbutanamide and dimethylaminophenyl-2-hydroxyphenylmethylene showed 32.8 and 32.7% activity respectively.

The three potent anti-inflammatory compounds, viz. 4a, b and d were further tested for their antiwrithmogenic activity in albino mice⁶. These compounds exhibited 25–50% protection against aconitine induced response whereas acetylsalicylic acid exhibited 70% protection at 40 mg/kg p.o. doses. As antiinflammatory activity in these three compounds were 50–57.8%, their ED₅₀ values were not determined.

In order to determine the safety margin of these compounds their ALD₅₀ values were also determined⁶. All these three compounds showed a large margin of safety as their ALD₅₀ values were >600 mg/kg p.o. (maximum dose tested) in albino mice.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. The compounds were routinely checked for their purity by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra on a Varian A 60 D instrument using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a JMSD 3000 spectrometer fitted with JMS 2000 data system.

N-Arylmethylene-2-methyl-5(4H)-oxazoline (1)⁶: A mixture of acetyl glycine (0.10 mmol) and substituted aromatic aldehyde (0.10 mmol) in acetic anhydride (20 ml) was heated for 2 h. On cooling, a gummy mass was obtained which was refluxed for 30 min in methanol (25 ml). The solid separated on cooling was washed and recrystallised from chloroform/petroleum ether: 1a, *N*-Phenylmethylene-2-methyl-5-4H-oxazoline (60%), m.p. 149°; 1b, *N*-4-*N*, *N*-dimethylaminophenylmethylene-2-methyl-5-4H-oxazoline (70%), m.p. 160°; 1c, *N*-2-hydroxyphenylmethylene-2-methyl-5-4H-oxazoline (70%), m.p. 110°; 1d, *N*-3,4-dimethoxyphenylmethylene-2-methyl-5-4H-oxazoline (70%), m.p. 166°.

β -Amino-N-(4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene)-1H-imidazol-1-yl (2): A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) and *o*-phenylenediamine was fused on a sooty flame till no more water separated from the reaction

mixture. The resulting solid was cooled and treated with methanol (10 ml). It was crystallised from ice-cold water and finally recrystallised from ethanol; 2a ν_{\max} 1 600 (C=O cyclic), 3 400 (NH₂), 1 660 (C=N) and 1 680 cm⁻¹ (C=O adjacent to NH).

β -Amino-N-2-[(4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene)-1H-imidazol-1-yl]phenylaminoacylbenzoate (3): A solution of 2 (0.01 mol) and *N*-protected amino acid (0.01 mol) in methylene chloride (60 ml) was cooled, then dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (0.015 mol) was added and stirred at room temperature for 8–10 h. The precipitated dicyclohexylurea was filtered off and the filtrate was washed successively with 1 *N* HCl, 1 *N* NaHCO₃ and a saturated solution of 1 *N* NaCl and dried on anhydrous sodium sulphate and left overnight. It was then filtered and excess of solvent was removed. The residue thus obtained was dissolved in benzene and kept aside for 2 h. The dicyclohexylurea which again precipitated out was filtered off. The solvent was removed at reduced pressure and the residue was crystallised from a mixture of benzene-petroleum ether to yield the products: 3a ν_{\max} 1 680 (C=O amidic), 3 400 (NH₂), 3 300 (NH), 1 360 (C=N) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (CH=C); δ (CDCl₃: DMSO) 1.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.6–8.0 (14H, m, ArH) and 5.2 (1H, s, NH adjacent to C=O).

β -Amino-N-2-[4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-arylmethylene-1H-imidazol-1-yl]phenyl-substituted-amide (4): A mixture of 3 (0.01 mol) and NaOH pellets (0.01 mol) in benzene was refluxed for 6 h. Excess of solvent was then removed and the solid separated was crystallised from petroleum ether and recrystallised from benzene/petroleum ether: 4c ν_{\max} 3 410 (NH₂), 1 660 (C=O in five-membered ring), 1 680 (C=O amidic) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (CDCl₃) 6.8–7.9 (9H, m, ArH), 4.8–5.4 (1H, bs, NH), 4.2–4.8 (2H, s, NH₂), 2.9 (3H, s, CH₃ aliph), 2.4 (1H, s, *exo*-CH), 1.8 (3H, s, CH₃-Ar) and 0.4–0.8 (1H, O, CH Se-C aliph); *m/z* 348 (*M*)⁺, 332 (*M*⁺-NH₂), 288 (352-C₂H₅OH), 262 (base peak 100%) (288-HCN), 247 (262-CH₃), 221 (247-CN), 119+102 (two fragments of 221), 91 and 77.

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